

EFFECTIVENESS OF PROGRAMME EVALUATION SYSTEMS IN MANAGEMENT TRAINING : A CASE STUDY ON BCS (ADMINISTRATION) ACADEMY

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1. Introduction

Training is a critical element in manpower development. Because of this fact, organizations pay a lot for training and development of their employees. At the same time, though it seems unbelievable, a very few organization, especially in the public sector, bothers about the outcome. Evaluation of participants is a common practice in Bangladesh whereas evaluation of objective is never done, although efforts to evaluate a training programme are not uncommon. But, in case of management training programme, evaluation is a must and efforts must not be limited to 'reaction-evaluation' only. In this paper, an attempt has been made to study the effectiveness of programme evaluation system in management training. Because of its leading role in management training at the public sector, Bangladesh Civil Service (Administration) Academy has been selected for the study which aim at according theoretical and empirical treatments to selected aspects of programme evaluation. Empirical data covering 1992-94 period, were mostly collected from files, registers and other unpublished documents of the Academy. Members of the faculty were interviewed and the author's personal knowledge of the functioning process of the Academy was of great use.

2. Why Evaluation :

The existence of a sound system of evaluation is a cornerstone for further improvement of a training programme. If we wish our programmes to be useful and effective we must evaluate. "The most Common reason for evaluation is to determine the effectiveness so future programmes can be improved." (Kirkpatrick, 1983 : 88). It was aptly summarized by Peter Warr et al, that evaluation consists of the collection, assessment and effective use of information concerning the following three questions :

- What needs to be changed ?

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- What Procedures are most likely to bring about this change ?
- What evidence is there that change has occurred ? (Warr, Bird, and Rackham 1990 : 15).

Evaluation is not a single activity, but a process (Nadler, 1989 : 40). As figure-1 suggests, it entails willingness for evaluations, selection of criteria, identification of basis for evaluation, selection of indicators, implementation of programme, collection of data, analysis and synthesis of data and changing the programmes as indicated by the findings of the evaluation.

Fig. 01 Evaluation Process :

Source : Laird, 1990 : 268

According to Matthew Miles, four imbalances may be noticed in any training programme : input overload, unrealistic goals, alienation of participants and linkage failure (Miles, 1964 : 437-90). As a result, basic objectives of the training remain unaccomplished. Evaluation tries to redress those imbalances in a training programme.

3. Programme Evaluation

There are three types of evaluations : (1) Evaluation of objectives, (2) Evaluation of participants and (3) Evaluation of training programmes. Again, three parties involved in evaluations include The Training Institute, The Participants and The Organization. The responsibility of carrying out the first type of evaluation lies with the organization, whereas the institution has to carry out the second type of evaluation. But programme evaluation is one thing which requires the combined and concerted efforts of the three parties involved. Programme evaluations may be of three types : (1) formative¹ one which should be carried out during the programme, (2) Summative² one which should be done at the end of the programme and (3) Follow-up evaluation after the completion of training programme at regular intervals.

Lynton and Pareek have developed a model for evaluation of training programme, where four main questions in terms of purpose has to be answered (Fig-2).

Effectiveness of the programme as a whole may be evaluated by applying both summative and follow-up evaluation techniques. Input evaluation may be carried out by applying formative technique. Among the four questions to be answered, there is no doubt that the first two are the most crucial. But remaining two are nonetheless important. In the backdrop of the above, an attempt will be made in the subsequent pages of this article to examine the programme evaluation system of Bangladesh Civil Service (Administration) Academy and its effectiveness.

4.0 BCS (Admin) Academy³.

4.1 The Academy

Bangladesh Civil Service (Administration) Academy was established in 1987. It was originally envisaged that the Academy would impart professional training to the new entrants and mid-level officers of the BCS (Admin) Cadre. Subsequently, the responsibility to organize and offer

professional training courses to the officers belonging to the BCS(foreign Affairs) Cadre was assigned to the Academy. The Academy is an attached department under the direct control of the Ministry of Establishment, government of Bangladesh. The Academy needs constant support from the M/O Estt. in its sustenance, continuation and strengthening of the functions assigned to it.

Figure-2 : Model for evaluation of training programme

Purpose	What ?	When ?	How ?	Who Evaluates ?
1) To improve the effectiveness of the programme as a whole	Contents and methods, including timing and sequences of training inputs	At end of programme and again at regular intervals after training	Generally available tools chosen in terms of training objectives of programme	Institution with the help of participants and their organizations
2) To increase effectiveness of different inputs and sequences of the training programme	Content and methods	Before and after inputs to be evaluated.	Specially designed tools, assignments etc.	Participants and trainers
3) To give the participants effective feedback to help them improve	Participants attitudes and behavior	Regularly during training	Tests, assignments questionnaires	Trainers and participants
4) To improve the trainers contribution	Trainer behavior and its effects	Regularly	Content analysis	Trainer with the help of colleagues and participants

Source : Lynton and Pareek, 1978 : 313

4.2 The Clientele

The Officers reporting to the Academy for training belong to the Administration and Foreign Affairs Cadres of the Bangladesh Civil Service. They are either new recruits or mid-level officers of the above two cadres who are selected on the basis of nation-wide competitive examination conducted by the Bangladesh Public Service Commission and appointed by the Government. The new recruits first undergo the Foundation Training course conducted by the Bangladesh Public Administration Training Centre (BPATC) , then report to the Academy for professional training. Though the academy has plan to organize training courses for mid-level officers but yet

to offer any. So far it has conducted courses for the new entrants who have joined the service through competition or absorption.

4.3 The Training Programmes

During the period under study (1992-94), alongside seminars , workshops and other activities , the Academy organized the following courses :

- a) Nine courses of four months' duration on Law and Administration for Assistant Commissioners of BCS (Admin) Cadre,
- b) Two Courses, one of nine months' and the other of six months' duration, on Foreign Affairs for the Assistant Secretaries of BCS (Foreign Affairs) Cadre, and
- c) Three orientation Courses for the new recruits in the BCS (Admin) Cadre.

4.4 The Objectives

The objectives of the training programmes offered by the Academy include the following :

- a) To improve knowledge in constitutional , international and criminal laws, land and revenue laws, various minor acts, rules and regulations, public administration, diplomacy and socio-economic development ;
- b) To turn out skilled , disciplined , responsible and committed officers with positive attitude and balanced development of mind and body ;
- c) To teach modern management skills through emphasis on practical training ;
- d) To develop team spirit so that the trainees can think , plan, organize and work in a group and
- e) To develop leadership quality .

5.0. Programme Evaluation System Of The Academy

The BCS (Admin) Academy usually follows , What it calls, ' two-way evaluation ' system : (i) evaluation of participants by the Academy and (2) evaluation of training programmes by the participants. As the first one is beyond the scope of the present article so the concentration will be upon the second one. The Academy is aware of the fact that the programme

evaluation by the participants only can determine internal validity of the programmes, but external validity can be measured and evaluated by evaluation of objectives involving the participants and their organizations with follow-up programmes which are yet to be carried out. The Academy adopts both formative and summative evaluation. Here, programme evaluation is divided into two parts: evaluation of trainer and evaluation of the course. They are discussed below in detail. After careful scrutiny of the programmes of the Academy, it is evident that four month long law and administration course for the Assistant Commissioners is the major programme which consumes approximately 80% efforts of the Academy. As such, attention will be focused upon this programme only.

5.1.0. Formative Evaluations

The followings come under this group which are carried out regularly during the courses:

5.1.1 Evaluation of Trainer (ET)

This evaluation is done by the participants which starts from the day one and covers all the topics presented by each trainer. Both the faculty and the guest trainers are evaluated with exception of training Managers, Viz., the Course Director and the Course Co-ordinators. They are evaluated as training Managers separately. During the process of this evaluation, individual trainees have to fill up daily the form no. Trg.-16/89 specially designed for this purpose. Trainees are divided into groups with a leader for each group. The group leader collects the forms filled up by his group members and then summarizes the opinions and fills up the form on Trg.-17/89 which is designed for the group leader. The trainee nominated as "Manager of the day" for every Saturday collects the filled up forms from the group leaders and submits those forms to the Research Section (RS) of the Academy. The Academy uses five-point scale to measure satisfaction with the trainer by putting number 05 for "Excellent" and number 01 for "Not satisfactory". As numerals do not always reflect the real situation so there is a provision for making comments by the participants. The RS analyzes the data, quantifies it in terms of percentage, and provides the findings to the course authority who utilizes it in selecting their trainer for the next week. Each of the trainers gets a copy of the findings along with the comments made by the participants so that they can utilize the findings for his/her improvement. According to the rules of the Academy, a guest trainer will be

dropped out of the programme if he fails to score at least 60, whereas the percentage is 50 for a member of the faculty . The member will get chance in the next course and if he fails again then he will be warned of by a demi-official letter. In case of consecutive third failure to score above 50 the Academy may ask the member of the faculty to quit .

5.1.2 Daily Programme Evaluation (DPE)

BCS(Admin) Academy form no. Trg.-15/89 is designed for the purpose of its daily evaluation programme . Only one participant has to fill up the form . Each of the participants , one by one, participates in this evaluation programme . This unique opportunity has been offered by the Academy to the participants to ventilate their feelings and comments daily, instead of waiting for a week or a month . By virtue of this evaluation, the chief executive and the course authority remain informed of everyday happenings and reactions. This evaluation covers all the daily programmes, which include the following :

- Physical Exercise early in the morning.
- Class room sessions.
- Games in the afternoon.
- Dining hall management of the day .
- Outdoor activities or extra-curricular activities(If any).
- Cleanliness of the building specially toilet.
- Management of the compound garden.
- Behaviour of officers and staff of the Academy.
- General remarks on the programmes of the day.

5.1.3 Monthly Programme Evaluation(MPE)

Every law and Administration course is measured and evaluated by all the participants at the end of first, second and third month. After collecting the duly filled in forms the RS compiles and analyzes the reponses and circulates the evaluation report among the faculty members. There is an Evaluation Appraisal Committee(EAC) which is headed by a Director of the Academy. EAC recommends measures to be taken; If the suggested measures affect any policy of the Academy, then approval of the faculty meeting, which is chaired by the chief executive, is needed ; Otherwise, direct requests are made to the course authority to do the needful

MPE, for which nominal scale is used, solicits responses concerning the following issues:

- Acceptability of trainers, training methods used and quality of reading materials supplied.
- Facilities in the classroom, availability and use of audio-visual training aids,
- Physical exercise, games, tea-attachment, and entertainment.
- Behavior of members of the faculty , course director, co-ordinator , other employees of the Academy and fellow participants.
- Name of the worst trainer and the least interesting subjects along side the most successful trainer and the most interesting.subjects.
- The most disliking experience at the Academy.
- General remarks , if any.

MPE is always included on the agenda of the regular faculty meeting. Sometimes, special meetings are convened to discuss the MPE report.

5.2.0 Summative Evaluation

At this stage, when the course is ended with ceremonial handing over of course-completion certificates, the participants, on their way back to their jobs, are asked to evaluate the whole training programme. At first, it was a written evaluation only. Subsequently, when the Academy found that the responses were inadequate, verbal evaluation was introduced. The Data collected from these evaluations are compiled and analyzed by the RS and evaluated by the faculty before the starting of next programme.

5.2.1 Written Evaluation

It is a written form of summative evaluation done at the end of the programme for which Academy form No. Trg.-6/88 (revised) has been developed using both nominal and ordinal scale. Structured and open-ended questions are also utilized.

This evaluation attempts to get responses about queries concerning the following :

- Expectations at the beginning.
- Level of fulfilment of expectations.

- Unfulfilled expectations.
- Accomplishment of the objective of the programme.
- Changes in knowledge, skills and attitude,
- Sequential arrangement of the programme.
- Training methodology.
- Audio-Visual aids.
- Relevancy of the programme contents and time allocated for each component.
- Duration of the Course.
- The best trainer of the programme.
- Overall management of the Course.
- Memorable as well as deplorable experience at the Academy.
- Suggestion for improvement.

5.2.2 Verbal Evaluation

It has been experienced at the Academy that the participants do not respond adequately at the written summative evaluation. At this time, the participants, bored with reading and writing, try to get rid of the lengthy evaluation form as quickly as possible and thus frustrates the purpose of the evaluation. To overcome this problem, the academy has introduced verbal summative evaluation. A three hour session is allocated for this purpose at the shut-down time of the programme. The session is presided over by the Chief Executive and attended by the faculty. The participants are asked to evaluate the programme in the way they wish. The proceedings of the session is supposed to be recorded and discussed at the faculty meeting.

5.3.0 Follow-up Evaluation

Realizing that formative and summative evaluations are not enough for the purpose of programme evaluation, the Academy has introduced follow-up evaluations. Under this programme, the members of the faculty including the Chief Executive visit district headquarters, the workplace of most of the clientele, and interacts with the ex-participants and their supervising officials. Two forms have been developed for this purpose : One for the

ex-participants and the other for their supervising officials. This evaluation aims at collecting data regarding the following :

- Changes in knowledge, skill and attitude.
- Adequacy of the programme.
- Application of acquired knowledge and skill.
- Necessity of Refreshers' Course.
- General remarks about the programme.

6.0 Shortcomings of the Evaluation System

The system of evaluation as practised in BCS (Administration) academy seems to be very effective. In reality, Achilles' heel is there. According to Dr. Saadat Hussain, "Trainers in Bangladesh are conversant with the above methods of evaluation. They, however, do not carry them out with the required regour because in absence of an alert and demanding leadership trainers also relapse to soft option (Hussain, 1995 : 83). BCS (Admin) Academy is not an exception to that notion.

The following shortcomings, which may be attributed to the aforesaid "soft option", have been observed in various programme evaluations of the Academy.

6.1 Evaluation of Trainers

This evaluation is found to be very effective except in two cases. Firstly, when it is concerned with top ranking government officials invited as trainer. As a matter of policy, any guest trainer who scores below 60 should be dropped. But it is not in practice in such cases because of the unwillingness on the part of the concerned training manager to drop such trainers. They are not even informed of poor rating. Yet it is a matter of satisfaction that the faculty is aware of the problem and trying to avoid such situations. Secondly, when the evaluation affects a member of faculty, he is supposed to be warned of. But it has been observed that no member of faculty has got warning for poor rating during the period under study. Again, no member of faculty was asked to quit the academy because of his poor performance although number of such failure is not negligible. Due to these factors, effectiveness of trainers' evaluation system has been reduced considerably. Another drawback is within the questionnaire itself. It is designed to measure the level of satisfaction only. What is missing is satisfaction of what ? It should be presentation, improvement of knowledge and/or relevance of the topic which are not reflected in the questionnaire.

6.2 Daily Programme Evaluation

Earlier it has been discussed that it has a great potentiality as an effective system. But its effectiveness was found to be much less than the expectations which may be attributed to the following factors :

- It has been observed that it required three days for circulation of the collected data during the first week. It required five days during the second and third week, seven days during the fourth week and afterwards it was not circulated at all.
- No one took the trouble to compile, compare and analyze the data.
- After some weeks, it became a routine matter--data was collected but not utilized.

6.3 Monthly Programme Evaluation

It is a vital tool for evaluation at the formative stage, but suffers from the following drawbacks :

- Undue delay in compilation of the data. It requires about 15 days. Then the RS distributes it among the faculty members.
- Though it is a convention that a special meeting should be convened to analyze and evaluate the data, yet, many a time, it got included on the agenda of a regular faculty meeting. As a result hasty disposal was inevitable frustrating the purpose of evaluation.
- It has been observed that on number of occasions, the collected data was not even discussed or evaluated at all. It specially happens in the third month of the programme.
- No effort has been noticed to have been made for a comparative analysis of data of different months of the programme.
- Evaluation Appraisal Committee was found to be totally inactive.

6.4 Summative Evaluation (Written)

The following are the shortcomings of this evaluation :

- It takes place at the end of the programme, usually on the day before the last day. Participants are in departing mood having the tendency to dispose it of hastily.

- Fewer responses to open-ended questions than on factual recall forms like yes/no or multiple choice questions.
- While developing the questionnaire, nominal scale has been used in the most cases. Such scale is capable of calculating mean, median and mode, but often leads to misleading conclusion.
- Out of 19 questions, only two uses ordinal scale which put items in rank order and capable of measuring abstract elements like perceptions and values.
- The percentile method of measurement is not in use.
- Inconsistency regarding point distribution in the opinion scale utilized is noticed. Out of six questions, two are in five-point group and other four questions are in four-point group.
- After the collection of data, no real analysis is done, let alone the comparative analysis.

6.5 Summative Evaluation (Verbal)

Imagine the situation : The participants are ready to depart bag and baggage, much bothered about dormitory clearance and anxious to get the long-awaited release order. At this very moment, they are asked to evaluate the training programme verbally. It is a three hour session which is often cut-short due to the pressing needs of the Chief Executive. Some times, it turned into a chatting session when the Chief was unable to attend it.

In a session like this, every one does not get the opportunity to express his views. The minority views may not be reflected ; at the sametime, opposite may happen also. Moreover, on many occasions, the proceedings was not reduced to writing. As a result, with the passage of time, it is very natural that every one has forgotten what was said or suggested.

6.6 Follow-up Evaluation

It is the latest addition in the series of efforts to evaluate the training programmes. But it has been found to be totally ineffective due to the following reasons :

- No concerted efforts has been made yet to collect the data.
- The questionnaire prepared for this purpose is totally inadequate.
- No analysis and appraisal has been done to identify the findings.

- The Academy has not yet utilized the data for any purpose.
- The proceedings of the discussions made by the Chief Executive with ex-participants and their superiors has not been documented, in most cases. As a result, the findings can not be utilized in future.

7. The Control Variables

No system runs in a vacuum. The overall environment comes into a shape by a complex interaction of many variables. It is not unnatural that some of the variables are controlling the others and the weaker variables can not attain the desired objectives without taking the controlling ones into consideration. In a training institute, evaluation system is a weak variable effectiveness of which is dependent upon the control variables like the following :

- Training institutes are often considered as a dumping ground for the misfits (Hussain, 1994 : 86). This affects the effectiveness of the system considerably.
- Lack of motivation on the part of the trainers.
- Negligent attitude towards research and evaluation department.
- Inertia in utilizing the findings of the evaluation.
- Lack of skilled personnel familiar with required statistical tools and techniques.
- Lack of evaluation of objectives of the training programmes.

It has also been observed that the course curricula has been thoroughly revised twice during the period under study. One might be surprised to know that neither any training need assessment was done nor the data collected by the RS was utilized for this purpose. Then how could it be done ? It was done with intuition guided by experience and thus nullifying the necessity for any programme evaluation system.

These are some of the major control variables, removal or at least reduction of which is a condition precedent to ensuring effectiveness of programme evaluation system in the Academy.

8. Conclusion

Presently, adequate arrangements has been made to train the civil servants. But to make these training programmes effective, real evaluation shall have

to be made instead of evaluation based on intuition guided by experience. As it has been observed in case of the Academy, the system of evaluation designed for the training programmes is more or less adequate. But the crux of the problem is the inertia in analyzing the collected data and inducing changes as per the findings of the evaluation. Given the control variables unchanged, it will be very difficult to intervene into the inertness. Needless to say, it requires a concerted effort on the part of the trainers, participants and the employer, i.e. the Government. Though this study and the findings are related to BCS (Administration) Academy only, yet it will be a mistake to assume that other training institutes are free from all these vices. In reality, it will not be irrational to generalize the findings of this study for all the training institutes in Bangladesh engaged in management training at least in the public sector.

NOTES

1. **Formative Evaluation** means doing some evaluating while the action is in progress without waiting for the final result.
2. **Summative Evaluation** means doing the evaluation when the programme is nearing completion.
3. This section of the article is based on **Introducing BCS (Administration) Academy** - a leaflet published by the Academy in 1990.

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